

Structured overview of thyroid hormone system disruption mechanisms, effects, and associated assays as a resource for the development of integrated approaches for testing and assessment

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1. Background

Recent advances in understanding thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) mechanisms and effects, as well as the development of new methods, have great potential to improve regulatory identification of endocrine disruptors (EDs). ED identification in the EU requires evidence of an adverse effect in an intact organism or its progeny (i.e., adversity), an endocrine mode of action (MoA) (i.e., endocrine activity), and a biologically plausible link between the two (EC 2017, 2018). In order to meet these criteria and at the same time foster implementation of new approach methodologies (NAMs) in line with the EU Roadmap towards phasing out animal testing (EC 2023), it is crucial that recent methodological advances are linked to existing knowledge on THSD mechanisms and effects. Here, we build on previous work on assembling a THSD adverse outcome pathway (AOP) network and assessing the domain of applicability (Knapen et al. 2020; Villeneuve et al. 2018; Haigis et al. 2023; Noyes et al. 2019) as well as a recent inventory of THSD methods (Vergauwen et al. 2024). The inventory presented 108 methods relevant to THSD, structured according to the five Levels of the Conceptual Framework (OECD 2018) comprising established methods (e.g., OECD *in vivo* Test Guidelines [TGs]) as well as citable methods that are under development, ready for validation or in the initial stages of validation. This includes 12 statistically validated *in silico* models (Level 1), 67 *in vitro* methods (Level 2), and around 30 *in vivo* assays (Levels 3–5).

This work supplements the study of Vergauwen et al. (2026), presenting an AOP network-based framework organizing information on THSD for use in regulatory assessments. Here, we provide an in-depth overview of the main mechanisms and effects related to THSD briefly summarized in Section 3 of Vergauwen et al. (2026). Table 1 and accompanying text provide more details regarding THSD mechanisms and effects, including the methods and supporting mechanistic information (mainly AOPs) that are currently available, and a note on the taxonomic, sex, and life-stage domains of applicability. The structure of this table is based on the mechanisms table suggested for Integrated Approach for Testing and Assessment (IATA)

development of non-genotoxic carcinogens by Jacobs et al. (2016). Molecular initiating events (MIEs) are presented in Section 2.1, structured according to the Blocks defined in the OECD Scoping Document for *in vitro* and *ex vivo* assays for the identification of modulators of thyroid hormone signaling (Murk et al. 2013; OECD 2014). The overview further includes main TH-specific (Section 2.2) and downstream key events (KEs) (Section 2.3) leading to adverse outcomes (AOs) (Section 2.4) that are part of OECD endorsed AOPs (Vergauwen et al. 2022a, 2022b, 2022c, 2022d, 2022e; Crofton et al. 2019; Rolaki et al. 2019), published AOPs under OECD review (Gözl et al. 2022) or generally well established and accepted thyroid mechanistic understanding (Bray and Sicard 1982; Crofton and Zoeller 2005; Hurley 1998).

This overview is intended as a resource for IATA development. Rather than being exhaustive, it provides a framework that also shows how information on additional mechanisms and effects may be included as it becomes available.

2. Main THSD mechanisms and effects

2.1. Molecular Initiating Events

2.1.1. Central regulation – Block #1

Thyroid hormones (TH) are regulated by a complex negative feedback loop involving the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis. Thyrotropin-Releasing Hormone (TRH), released from the hypothalamus, and thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), released from the pituitary, along with their receptors in the pituitary (TRHR) and thyroid (TSHR), respectively, represent upstream central regulators of the HPT axis. Upon their respective receptor-binding, TRH and TSH can stimulate the synthesis of TH or proliferation of thyroid follicles in the thyroid gland. Therapeutic small-molecule ligands for auto-immune diseases (e.g. thyroid stimulating antibody) have been shown to activate TSH receptor and result in biological effects similar to those of TSH, causing hyperthyroidism (Takasu et al. 2001). Despite reports indicating an effect of some EDs (e.g. PCB 153 and DEHP) on TRHR and TSHR, respectively increasing and decreasing their expression (Liu et al. 2015; Sun et al. 2022), evidence demonstrating a direct interaction of chemicals with TRH or TSH receptors is currently lacking (Köhrle 2026).

2.1.2. TH synthesis – Block #2

TH synthesis in the thyroid gland can be reduced by inhibition of thyroperoxidase (TPO) or the Na⁺/I⁻ symporter (NIS). Lower levels of TH thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) synthesis is typically followed by decreased serum T4 levels and compensatory increases in TSH, causing thyroid gland weight increase, hypertrophy, and hyperplasia (OECD 2014).

Chemical exposure has been shown to inhibit TPO or NIS function and thereby disrupt TH synthesis (Köhrle 2026). It is important to note that the developing embryo relies on the maternal supply of THs during the earliest developmental stages, until its developing thyroid gland becomes functional (Alt et al. 2006). Therefore, in species with external embryonic development, TH-regulated processes during early embryogenesis are expected to be less responsive to inhibitors of TH synthesis. On the other hand, inhibition of TH synthesis in females during the reproduction period or early gestation (in mammals) can be critical due to the sensitive window of development.

2.1.3. Binding and transport in serum – Block #3

In serum, TH binding and transport is facilitated by plasma proteins. In humans, about 99.8% of the circulating TH is bound to plasma protein to facilitate transport (Goodman 2009). Altering TH binding to serum transporters thyroxine-binding prealbumin (TTR) or thyroxine-binding globulin (TBG) may,

therefore, impact TH transport in the serum and availability to target tissues, with subsequent effects on total serum levels through feedback mechanisms. In humans, TH transport in serum is mainly carried by TBG, reportedly accounting for approximately 70% of the total protein-bound hormone (Goodman 2009). However, it has been suggested that TTR is crucial for TH transport across the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier (Kassem et al. 2006; Köhrle 2026).

In vitro screens and predictive structure-based models identified a large number of chemicals that bind to TH transporters, including polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), and perfluorinated compounds (Cao et al. 2010; Meerts et al. 2000; Weiss et al. 2009). Several of these chemicals, such as tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), are known to alter TH levels, and TTR binding might, therefore, contribute to mediate their THSD effects (Liao et al. 2024). TTR binding tends to be more documented than TBG, with a possibly larger domain of applicability.

2.1.4. Metabolism and excretion – Block #4

When transported in the serum, metabolism and excretion of TH occurs in various peripheral organs and tissues.

Deiodinase inhibition

Deiodinase (DIO) enzymes are important to alter the levels of the more biologically active TH T3. Some T3 is directly produced by the thyroid gland, but deiodinase 1 (DIO1) and 2 (DIO2) can increase T3 levels via deiodination of T4 or decrease it by DIO3 activity (Bruinstroop, van der Spek, and Boelen 2023). The relative role of the different deiodinases in systemic vs. peripheral T3 production in tissues and potential differences across vertebrates are still a matter of debate. Although the relative contribution of DIO1 *versus* DIO2 varies between species, tissues, and developmental stages, several lines of evidence indicate some redundancy between both enzymes, DIO2 probably playing a predominant role (Bagci et al. 2015; Stinckens et al. 2020; Schneider et al. 2001; Schneider et al. 2006; Galton et al. 2009; Maia et al. 2005). The role of DIO2 might be even more critical in teleosts than in mammals (Orozco and Valverde 2005; van der Spek, Fliers, and Boelen 2017; Houbrechts et al. 2016).

In rodents, the phenotypes remain relatively mild when both deiodinases are disrupted, probably due to the compensatory thyroid production of T3 (Galton et al. 2009). On the other hand, the severity of phenotypes associated with DIO3 disruption highlights the particular importance of its protective role against excessive cellular levels of T3 both in mammals and fish (Bagci et al. 2015; Hernandez et al. 2006; Hernandez et al. 2021).

Deiodinases are potential targets for chemicals (Köhrle 2026). Halogenated compounds, such as PBDEs and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), have the potential to bind and inhibit deiodinases through halogen binding (Marsan and Bayse 2020, 2017), and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) was shown to inhibit DIO1 and DIO2 (Stinckens et al. 2018).

Interference with liver clearance

TH homeostasis can also be affected by glucuronidation and sulfation of THs in the liver, which results in their excretion. Enhanced clearance of T4 from the serum, due to induction of hepatic enzymes like UDP-glucuronosyltransferase (UGT) lowers serum T4 levels and raises TSH levels, which disrupts the normal functioning of the HPT-axis feedback loop (and thus possibly thyroid function and development) (Kortenkamp et al. 2017).

Several lines of evidence support mechanisms involving hepatic nuclear receptor-mediated TH clearance in chemical-induced alteration in THs levels. Known agonists of xenobiotic receptors such as the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR), pregnane X receptor (PXR) and constitutive androstane receptor (CAR) (e.g., tetrachlorodibenzodioxin (TCDD) or PCB 126) were shown to increase the activity of metabolic enzymes, including glucuronidases (UGT), with a consequent decrease in T4 and T3 serum levels and a compensatory increase in TSH level (Fisher et al. 2006; Nishimura et al. 2005; Paul et al. 2012; Paul et al. 2010). Such a mode of action might also underly triclosan-mediated THSD, although the involvement of hepatic nuclear receptors might be species dependent, with species differences in ligand binding, and rather limited in mice (Paul et al. 2012; Paul et al. 2010). Conversely, inhibition of UGT activity, caused by decreased AhR gene/protein expression, may underly the increase of T3 and T4 serum levels in mice exposed to styrene trimer or carrying specific mutations (Gessner et al. 2012; Yanagiba et al. 2008).

2.1.5. Local cellular concentrations – Block #5

Transportation of TH into various types of cells is facilitated by specific TH transporter proteins embedded in the plasma membrane. These include, but are not limited to, organic anion transporting polypeptides (OATP1C1, OATP1A2, OATP3A1) (Landers and Richard 2017), L-type amino acid transporters (LAT1/2) (Friesema et al. 2001), SCL17A4 (Friesema et al. 2008) and monocarboxylate transporters (MCT8/10) (Pizzagalli et al. 2002). The most specific TH transporter currently identified is monocarboxylate transporter 8 (MCT8) (Teumer et al. 2018).

The importance of the TH transporters is highlighted by mutations in the genes of the transporters resulting in inactivation. The most obvious example is the transporter-inactivating mutation of the MCT8 gene that causes Allan-Herndon-Dudley syndrome (AHDS), which is characterized by severe cognitive impairment, muscle weakness and poor muscle tone (Schwartz and Stevenson 2007). Also, a mutated OATP1C1 was associated with impaired cognitive and motor functioning in a 15-year old patient (Stromme et al. 2018). Transport and expression of the transporters is tissue-specific, and disruptions in TH transport will lead to altered (i.e. reduced) cellular levels of THs in various organs systems or tissues (Noyes et al. 2019). TH transport is also crucial in various barriers such as the placental barrier, blood brain barrier and cerebrospinal fluid barrier. MCT8/10, OATP1C1 and LAT1/2 are known to be expressed in the mammalian brain. However, the level of expression of these transporters appears to differ between species. Mice lacking functional *Mct8* expression do not show similar neurological impairment as humans with a mutation in the MCT8 gene. This is suggested to be a result of an increased expression of another transporter, *Oatp1c1* (Bernal, Guadano-Ferraz, and Morte 2015). Also, TH transporters have been identified in zebrafish, including the genes encoding *mct8/10* and *oatp1c1* (Zada, Blitz, and Appelbaum 2017). Multiple stressors have been identified that act on these transporters such as silyristin (an MCT8 inhibitor), lesinurad (an OATP transport inhibitor), 2-Amino-2-norbornanecarboxylic acid (BCH) (an LAT1 and LAT2 inhibitor) and TBBPA (an OATP1C1 inhibitor) (Chen et al. 2023; Wagenaars et al. 2024a; Wagenaars et al. 2024b; Wagenaars et al. 2025).

2.1.6. Cellular responses – Block #6

TH effects can be mediated by thyroid hormone receptors α and β (THR α and β), nuclear receptors which heterodimerize with retinoid X receptor (RXR) to transactivate the expression of target genes. By binding to THRs, THs regulate, among others, development, growth and metabolism. THR α is mainly expressed in heart, brain and bone, whereas THR β is predominant in liver, kidneys, pituitary gland, and brain, also participating in metabolism regulation. In addition, THR β is particularly important for the feedback regulation of HPT axis (Rehman et al. 2023).

Several chemicals have chemical structures that are similar to THs, and may bind to THR_s, acting either as agonists (such as OH-PCBs) or antagonists, displacing the binding of T₃ and dysregulating the expression of target genes. Due to the importance of THR_s during brain development, exposure to such chemicals during gestation may have severe consequences (Ghassabian and Trasande 2018). However, THR_s appear to be highly selective, and a limited number of chemicals have been shown to bind these receptors e.g. novel drugs and TBBPA (Schapira et al. 2003). THR mediation was also considered a lower priority for TG development in the OECD scoping document (OECD 2014).

2.2. TH-specific key events

All the above MIEs are important for TH regulation in serum and tissues, after which TH specific key events (KEs) occur;

2.2.1. Thyroid gland goiter and histopathological changes

Increased thyroid weight (goitre) and thyroid follicle hyperplasia and/or hypertrophy observed through histopathology reflects a compensatory response of the thyroid follicles to decreased circulating TH levels and is therefore considered an indirect measurement of decreased TH levels or reduced TH synthesis (a KE in several AOPs) in different vertebrata taxa (Axelstad et al. 2008; Bradford et al. 2005; Olker et al. 2018; Patino et al. 2003; Pannetier et al. 2023; Ramhoj et al. 2022; Tietge et al. 2010). It may result from different mechanisms reducing circulating TH levels, and is based on decreased negative feedback with increased secretion of TRH and TSH which stimulates thyroid follicles to grow. In the case of thyroid adenoma/carcinoma in rodents, it also is a causal event leading to the development of adenomas/carcinomas.

2.2.2. Altered hormone (TH and TSH) levels

Altered TH (mainly (T₄) and (T₃)) levels function as central hubs in the mechanistic model resulting from various MIEs affecting their synthesis, metabolism, transport, and cellular action, and leading to various AOs. Evaluating the effects on TH levels is therefore critical for identifying THSD chemicals. The interplay between TSH and THs is a pivotal component of endocrine regulation, orchestrated through a complex negative feedback loop involving the HPT axis. In short, the hypothalamic TRH and the pituitary TSH stimulate the thyroid gland to produce THs which, in turn, provide negative feedback, inhibiting the release of TRH and TSH from the hypothalamus and pituitary gland. Adverse perturbation in this feedback loop can lead to thyroid disorders, including hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism (Brent 2012; Jameson, Mandel, and Weetman 2017; Ross et al. 2016; Yen 2001).

Effects on THs, and, to a lesser extent, TSH levels, have been documented for several chemicals, such as PCBs, PBDEs, BPA, perchlorate, or phthalate, acting through various MIEs (Boas, Feldt-Rasmussen, and Main 2012; Vuong et al. 2018). Whilst most mammalian studies report serum levels, in small samples, such as those from fish early life stages, mostly whole-body TH levels are reported. Overall, there is less evidence on local tissue levels, which is technically more challenging but biologically more relevant. For example, disruption of TH transport proteins, such as MCT8, or deiodinases may alter local TH concentrations in tissues despite normal serum levels, resulting in developmental and functional impairments (OECD 2014; Pannetier et al. 2023; Hassan et al. 2020; Hassan et al. 2017). In addition, consistency across studies in the timing of sampling, which strongly influences hormone levels, could still be improved to harmonize the interpretation of the results.

Several AOPs, including endorsed ones, depict events leading to and resulting from a decrease in TH levels. Yet fewer AOPs, mostly for amphibians, describe a mechanism involving an increase in T₄ (four AOPs) or

T3 (one AOP). While increases in TSH levels are generally an indication of hypothyroidism based on negative feedback, knowledge of chemicals clearly acting through altered TSH levels as a causative event/ mode of action remains limited (e.g., AOPs 110, 119, and 162 leading to thyroid adenoma/carcinoma).

2.3. Downstream key events

Downstream of the TH-specific KEs, various effects can occur;

2.3.1. Cellular/tissue KEs related to neurodevelopment

Altered hippocampal anatomy

An important temporal lobe brain structure is the hippocampus, and this region is involved in cognition, learning, and memory. Postnatally, the hippocampus generates new neurons in various zones of the hippocampus and that makes its morphology unique. This neuronal production consists of multiple steps and processes, including a number of developmental phases, such as self-renewal of neural stem cells, the facilitation of continued division of precursor cells to produce new granule cells, and subsequent differentiation and migration of these new cells into the granule cell layer of the hippocampus (Hodge et al. 2012; Sibbe and Kulik 2017). Normal hippocampal development depends upon sufficient THs for full maturation and proper function during the development period of the hippocampus (Rivas and Naranjo 2007). It is known that adverse effects on cognition development are usually due to abnormal hippocampal structure or function (Jarrard 1993).

Level of BDNF reduced

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) plays a crucial role in the normal development of the central nervous system. It is involved in neurogenesis, neural circuit formation, neurite outgrowth, synaptogenesis and synapse maturation and stabilization (Schinder and Poo 2000; Trajkovska et al. 2007). A decrease in BDNF expression is associated with various neurodevelopmental, neuropsychiatric, and neurodegenerative disorders (Autry and Monteggia 2012; Camuso et al. 2022; Lima Giacobbo et al. 2019). BDNF is expressed in most vertebrates, including zebrafish, rodents, and mammals (Aid et al. 2007; Cacialli et al. 2016; Trajkovska et al. 2007). Furthermore, BDNF levels in the brain are regulated by thyroid hormones and the connection between hypothyroidism, reduced BDNF levels and cognitive defects described as learning and memory was shown in rat pups (Shafiee, Vafaei, and Rashidy-Pour 2016). Several chemicals have been associated with changing BDNF levels, including potential THSD chemicals, such as BPA, TBBPA or PBDE (Spinu et al. 2022; Mustieles et al. 2020; Mustieles et al. 2022).

Decreased synaptogenesis

THs influence different processes in the brain, including synaptogenesis (Bernal, Guadano-Ferraz, and Morte 2003; Bernal 2005). Synapses are specialized in the fast transfer of neurotransmitters from a pre- to a postsynaptic neuron. Synaptogenesis, the formation of synapses in the brain, is regulated by BDNF and TH. Synaptogenesis can be influenced by neural activity, which enables the neurons to maintain neural homeostasis and adapt to new conditions (Qi et al. 2022). Synaptogenesis of various neurons within a network will be involved in neuronal network formation. Neural networks are essential to produce complex behaviours such as learning and memory (Mayford, Siegelbaum, and Kandel 2012). Studies show that hypothyroidism affects BDNF levels, reduces synaptogenesis, and induces cognitive defects described as learning and memory in pups (Shafiee, Vafaei, and Rashidy-Pour 2016). This process is also described in existing AOPs e.g. 13, 42 and 54.

Hypomyelination

Decreased myelination (hypomyelination) regulated via oligodendrocytes can lead to 'cognition' and 'motor function' defects. Oligodendrocytes are a type of glial cells in the central nervous system and oligodendrocytes are mainly involved in myelination. Throughout development, oligodendrocytes are generated from oligodendrocyte progenitor cells and undergo a strict process of proliferation, migration and differentiation. After differentiation they finally produce a critically important protective sheath coating of myelin (Bradl and Lassmann 2010). Myelin is crucial for the conduction of action potentials in the central nervous system. Myelin is needed for fast communication across neural networks and makes it crucial for proper motor sensory function and cognition (Jakovcevski et al. 2009; Saab and Nave 2017).

THs are involved in multiple steps in the maturation of progenitor cells into oligodendrocyte. TH stimulates proliferation of oligodendrocyte progenitor cells into the generation of oligodendrocytes. Also, TH is necessary to obtain adequate oligodendrocyte numbers. Then, TH stimulates functional and morphological maturation of the oligodendrocyte by increasing the expression of myelin basic protein and proteolipid protein in the human fetal brain. In rats, it has been shown that deficiencies in TH during brain development result in altered expression of myelin and impaired oligodendrocyte cell cycle. Hypothyroidism resulted in impaired oligodendrocyte myelination in zebrafish embryos, with T3 supplementation restoring myelination (Farias-Serratos et al. 2021). Brain MRI of patients with MCT8 mutations showed delayed myelination, reduced cerebral white matter volume and periventricular white matter lesions (Groeneweg et al. 2020). In *mct8* deficient zebrafish, the transcription of myelin-related genes was altered, neuronal circuit formation impaired, and the cellular organisation of the central nervous system and brain development were affected (Vatine et al. 2013; de Vrieze et al. 2014; Zada et al. 2014).

Heterotopia

Heterotopia is characterised as an abnormal cluster of neurons and is currently suggested as an endpoint for THSD, especially in rats. Although heterotopia can also occur in humans, a direct causal link with THSD in humans has yet to be made (Hassan et al. 2017; O'Shaughnessy et al. 2018; O'Shaughnessy et al. 2019). However, not all chemicals that perturb the thyroid system will induce heterotopia, since heterotopia is dependent upon the chemical's mode of action and the window of exposure (O'Shaughnessy et al. 2018). Furthermore, animal studies show that hypothyroidism results in other brain related effects such as neurobehavioural effects, learning and memory effects, or locomotor effects and histological effects, e.g., disruption of the granular layers in the cerebellum or altered hippocampus morphology.

2.3.2. Impaired eye development

Eye development is known to be regulated by THs across vertebrates (Viets, Eldred, and Johnston 2016) and THSD has been shown to result in impacts on eye development such as reduced eye size, altered retinal layer structure, and altered photoreceptor patterning (e.g., (Ng et al. 2010; Baumann et al. 2016)). Ophthalmopathies are also commonly reported in human patients with thyroid diseases (both hyperthyroidism, as in Graves' disease, and hypothyroidism, as in Hashimoto's thyroiditis) (Sawicka-Gutaj et al. 2021; Jankauskiene and Jarusaitiene 2012). An AOP has been developed that focuses on the disruption of the retinal layers' development as a result of reduced TH levels in fish (Gözl et al. 2022; AOP 363), e.g., alterations in the photoreceptor layer and retinal pigment epithelium (Baumann et al. 2016; Gözl et al. 2024a; Gözl et al. 2024b). The chain of events is plausibly applicable across vertebrates, and altered retinal layer structure with subsequent alterations in visual function may be relevant for both environmental and human health. For example, in rats with congenital hypothyroidism, alterations in the photoreceptor and ganglion cell layer were observed (Gamborino et al. 2001). Some uncertainties remain, especially related to the exact underlying mechanisms and timing during development (Gözl et al. 2022).

2.3.3. Impaired swim bladder inflation

Swim bladder inflation in fish is known to be under TH control (Brown et al. 1998; Liu and Chan 2002). Reduced swim bladder inflation resulting from TPO and DIO inhibition has been described in WPHA/WNT endorsed AOPs 155-159 (Vergauwen et al. 2022a, 2022b, 2022c, 2022d, 2022e), and is supported by chemical exposures in zebrafish, fathead minnows and medaka (Jomaa et al. 2014; Cavallin et al. 2017; Stinckens et al. 2018; Horie et al. 2022; Horie et al. 2024) as well as in knockdown/knockout and TH supplementation studies in zebrafish embryos (Walpita et al. 2009; Walpita, Crawford, and Darras 2010; Heijlen et al. 2014; Bagci et al. 2015; Houbrechts et al. 2016). Whilst the Medaka has one swim bladder chamber which inflates during larval development, in zebrafish and fathead minnows, the first (posterior) chamber of the swim bladder inflates during embryonic development, but the second (anterior) chamber inflates later during larval development. In these species, posterior chamber inflation was shown to be less responsive to inhibition of TH synthesis (Stinckens et al. 2018; Stinckens et al. 2016; Nelson et al. 2016), likely because the most sensitive processes of posterior chamber development occur before the time when endogenous TH synthesis becomes active, and seem to rely mostly on maternally transferred THs (Van Dingenen et al. 2023; Fagundes et al. 2024). Both chambers have a role in buoyancy and thus in swimming performance and the anterior chamber has an additional role in facilitating hearing.

2.4. Adverse outcomes

Various adverse outcomes (AOs) are associated with THSD in mammals, fish and amphibians on an individual level, such as;

2.4.1. Cognitive, learning, memory deficits

Different clinical examples or genetic studies illustrate the importance of TH homeostasis and the diverse and severe consequences of its perturbation beyond normal physiological boundaries, especially for brain development. A causal link between thyroid hormone disruption and cognition, learning and memory defects is mainly shown by genetic studies that show inactivation of various TH transporters, such as the MCT8 gene, resulting in AHDS, which is characterized by severe cognitive impairment, muscle weakness and poor muscle tone (Schwartz and Stevenson 2007). OATP1C1 mutation resulted in impaired cognitive and motor functioning. Utilising magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), degeneration of central white matter was observed, and the patient showed abnormal energy metabolism (Stromme et al. 2018). But also, less severe mutations in the transporters show cognitive effects (Groeneweg et al. 2025). In addition, the importance of TH action for cognition is also shown in patients with a heterozygous frameshift mutation in THRA which suffer from psychomotor and cognitive disabilities with varying degrees of severity (van Mullem et al. 2012).

Chemicals can interfere with TH levels during brain development with various susceptibilities throughout life stages, including effects on cognitive function and learning and memory as shown by some epidemiology studies. The Swedish Environmental Longitudinal, Mother and child, Asthma and allergy (SELMA) study, in which 95% of the pregnant women were recruited before week 14 of gestation, found that both hypothyroxinemia and subclinical hypothyroidism have been associated with a decrease in IQ scores which highlights the importance of studies investigating the effects of THSDs on neurodevelopment (Levie et al. 2018). Multiple AOPs have already been developed for TH homeostasis and adverse effects on cognition, learning and memory defects, for example AOPs with ID number 12, 13, 42, 54 and 134 on the AOP-Wiki).

2.4.2. Loss of cochlear function, visual dysfunction

In addition to impaired development of the central nervous system, THSD has been related to impaired neurosensory development across vertebrates (briefly reviewed by Haigis et al. 2023). This includes altered visual dysfunction through, for example, impaired development of the retina (Gözl et al. 2022; AOP 363), reduced eye size and altered photoreceptor patterning. Especially in mammals, hypothyroidism has also been linked to impaired cochlear development and reduced hearing (Crofton and Rice 1999; Crofton and Zoeller 2005; AOP 8). In fish, the swim bladder also plays a role in hearing (see section 2.3.3 on impaired swim bladder inflation). The importance of functional hair cells for neurosensory function also relates to the development of the neuromasts in the lateral line of fish, which has been shown to be impacted by THSD (Besson et al. 2020; Hu et al. 2019; Vandeputte et al. 2026). Additionally, reduced olfactory function has been linked to THSD.

2.4.3. Thyroid follicular tumours

In rodents, increased occurrence of thyroid follicular tumours (adenomas/carcinomas) has been linked to an increase in TSH levels which over-stimulate thyroid cell growth leading to hypertrophy of follicular cells. TSH increase is a consequence of T4 serum decrease which may be mainly determined by enhanced clearance through upregulation of glucuronyltransferase activity (Dellarco et al. 2006; Papineni et al. 2015; Rouquie et al. 2014; Wilson et al. 1996), but also by decreased TH synthesis due to NIS or TPO inhibition (Hurley 1998). In rodents, circulating TSH levels are generally higher in males than in females. Accordingly, male rats display a higher incidence of thyroid tumours upon exposure to THS disruptors, compared to females (Hurley 1998). The relevance of this AO in humans is still under debate due to the lower susceptibility of human thyroid; this may be ascribed, amongst other mechanisms, to the presence of thyroid hormone binding globulin (THBG) which is lacking in rodents. THBG affects the amount of free circulating THs and their bioavailability for metabolism and excretion (Hurley 1998). Therefore, this mechanism is generally considered not to be human-relevant based on EU CLP Criteria (Bartsch et al. 2018).

2.4.4. Impaired swimming

Impaired swimming performance has been observed in fish with impaired swim bladder inflation and visual function (Stinckens et al. 2020; Cavallin et al. 2017; Gözl et al. 2022; Horie et al. 2022; Walter et al. 2019; Zada et al. 2014). It should be noted that swimming performance in itself only constitutes one part of the entire behavioural response and is not solely related to neurodevelopment. This complicates the identification of specific causes of impaired swimming performance. Whilst direct evidence linking reduced swimming performance to reduced survival is scarce (Handelsman, Claireaux, and Nelson 2010), for fish as well as for other free-swimming aquatic species (e.g., amphibians or invertebrates), swimming performance is essential for foraging, mating and predator avoidance (Scott and Sloman 2004; Watkins 1996; Faimali et al. 2017; Trekels, Van de Meutter, and Stoks 2012) and thus has clear population relevance. There is clear evidence of reduced swim bladder inflation leading to reduced survival (Czesny, Graeb, and Dettmers 2005; Woolley and Qin 2010; Kindschi and Barrows 1993; Egloff 1996), which is plausibly related to reduced swimming performance.

2.4.5. Impaired metamorphosis

Thyroid hormones play an important role in the metamorphosis of amphibians (Gudernatsch 1912), and the changing and fine-tuning of TH levels during tadpole development, plays a specific and crucial role in the successful completion of amphibian metamorphosis (Bray and Sicard 1982). The first stages of tadpole development are characterized by the development of larval structures and body growth or early metamorphosis up to Nieuwkoop and Faber (NF) stage 55 (Nieuwkoop and Faber 1975), and are independent on the presence of TH hormone. However, the further growth and the development of

extremities up to stage 60, is dependent on a surge of thyroid hormone and decreased TH levels result in delayed or complete lack of the development of hind and front limbs. The final stages of late metamorphosis, up to NF stage 66, marking the successful completion of metamorphosis, are characterised by body shape remodelling and decreasing TH levels (Etkin 1932; Nieuwkoop and Faber 1975). The relevance of assays using amphibian metamorphosis as an endpoint has been shown by the decreased percentage of metamorphosed tadpoles reported after exposure of tadpoles to sediment extracts via water (Fort et al. 2000) or diet (Gutleb et al. 2007).

3. Table 1: Main mechanism/effect components of THSD, and suggested organisation for IATA development

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
MOLECULAR INITIATING EVENTS							
Central regulation (Block #1)							
TSH receptor agonism	Activation of TSHR in the thyroid follicles triggers production of TH.	NETVAL Method 1b: Thyrotropin-stimulating hormone (TSH) receptor activation based on cAMP measurement (TM2019-03 (EU)). Optimizing protocol, including antagonist measurement, and identifying active chemicals are needed for further validation.	There are no KEs representing TSH receptor agonism or antagonism in the AOP-wiki.* TSH released from the pituitary positively regulates the synthesis and release (secretion) of thyroid hormones (T3 and T4) from the thyroid gland (Szkudlinski et al. 2002). TSH receptor controls transcription and posttranslational modification of NIS (Dai, Levy, and Carrasco 1996).	Interaction with auto-immune disorder: aberrant TSHR signaling by autoantibodies leads to Graves' disease and hypothyroidism (Duan et al. 2022).	-	Small-molecule ligands as therapeutic agents for auto-immune diseases. stimulating antibody (TSAb) can activate TSHR and produce biological effects similar to those of TSH, causing hyperthyroidism	Plausibly relevant across vertebrates. Plausibly relevant across all life stages. THs are regulated by the TSH receptor and are critical for normal brain development and maturation and other organ systems. Plausibly relevant to both sexes
TSH receptor antagonism	Inhibition/blocking of TSHR in the thyroid follicles stops production of TH						
TRH receptor agonism	Activation of the TRH receptor in the pituitary triggers the synthesis and secretion of TSH.	NETVAL Method 1a; PATHHUNTER@ BETA-ARRESTIN thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) receptor activation (beta-galactosidase) measuring agonist and antagonist activities (TM-2019-02 (EU)). No validation pending.	There are no KEs representing TRH receptor agonism or antagonism in the AOP-wiki.* TRH stimulates the secretion of Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone (TSH) from the anterior pituitary gland upon binding to TRHR.	Intra network: TRH stimulation of TRHR1 leads to activation of phospholipase C, Ca ⁺⁺ mobilization and activation of PKC (Abe et al. 2004). TRH activates not only the secretion of TSH but also the transcription of TSH β and α -glycoprotein (α GSU) subunit genes. TSH β subunit expression is maintained by two transcription factors, Pit1 and GATA2, and is negatively regulated by thyroid hormone (T3) (Ohba et al. 2011) Inter network: The fundamental excitatory actions of TRH throughout the neuroaxis result from blocking various K ⁺ channels linked to G-protein coupled TRH receptors in neurons and pituitary cells in distinct TRH-innervated anatomical pathways; the functional consequences of blockade of these K ⁺ channels are to enhance neuronal and secretory outputs in TRH	-	No prototypical chemicals identified for TRH receptor (ant)agonism	Plausibly relevant across vertebrates. Plausibly relevant across all life stages. Plausibly relevant to both sexes
TRH receptor antagonism	Blocking of the TRH receptor in the pituitary inhibits the synthesis and secretion of TSH.						

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
				regulatory circuits to modulate behavioral and energy homeostasis (Yarbrough et al. 2007)			
TH synthesis (Block #2)							
TPO inhibition	Many environmental chemicals have TPO inhibition potential and inhibition of TH synthesis has a direct and crucial impact on the THS.	NETVAL method 2a: Thyroperoxidase (TPO) inhibition based on oxidation of Amplex UltraRed (TM2019-04 (EU)). Under validation. NETVAL method 2c: Tyrosine iodination using liquid chromatography (TM2019-06 (EU)) were selected for further validation. Under validation.	MIE 279 “Thyroperoxidase, Inhibition” leads to decreased TH synthesis and decreased T4 serum levels. It is part of: 2 WPHA/WNT-endorsed AOPs: AOP 42 leading to decreased cognitive function in mammals AOP 159 leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation in fish are . 1 AOP under review: AOP 363 leading to altered visual function. 2 AOPs under development: AOP 119 leading to thyroid carcinoma in rodents AOP 402 leading to heterotopia in rats (currently no KERs have been included in this AOP).	TPO activity depends on the co-localized membrane partner and catalytic generator of H ₂ O ₂ , dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2) (Fortunato et al. 2010). TPO function depends on the NIS-mediated iodide transport into thyroid. The AOP 271 (under development) describes the links between TPO inhibition and reduced fecundity in fish.	-	Methimazole, 6-propylthiouracil, amitrole Genistein	High level of confidence for the applicability of TPO inhibition to mammals and fish and a moderate confidence level for amphibians. Plausibly applicable to reptiles and birds based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023). Plausibly relevant to life stages where TH synthesis is active. Plausibly relevant to both sexes.
NIS inhibition	Intracellular uptake of iodide by thyroid cells is crucial for TH synthesis and involves the Na ⁺ /I ⁻ Symporter (NIS).	NETVAL method 2d: Inhibition of the sodium iodide symporter (NIS) based on Sandell-Kolthoff reaction (TM2019-07 (EU)).	MIE 424 “Inhibition, NA ⁺ /I ⁻ symporter (NIS)” is expected to lead to reduced TH synthesis and mutation in NIS in humans leads to hypothyroidism. It is part of: 1 WPHA/WNT-endorsed AOP: AOP 54 leading to learning and memory impairment). 3 AOP under development: AOP 134 leading to adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes in mammals, AOP 176 “leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis, and AOP 110 leading to follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas (in rat and mouse). The AOP 65 leading to adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes in mammals is not under active development.		-	Perchlorate Thiocyanate Nitrate	High level of confidence for the applicability of NIS inhibition to mammals, moderate level of evidence for fish and amphibians. Plausibly applicable to reptiles and birds based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023) Plausibly relevant to life stages where TH synthesis is active. Plausibly relevant to both sexes

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
Binding and transport in serum (Block #3)							
TTR binding	Disruption of TH transport alters TH levels	<p>NETVAL Method 3b: Thyroxine-binding prealbumin (TTR) binding using fluorescence displacement (T4-FITC) (TM2019-09 (EU))</p> <p>NETVAL Method 3a: Thyroxine-binding prealbumin (TTR) / thyroxine-binding globulin (TBG) binding using fluorescence displacement (ANSA) (TM2019-08 (EU)) (Montano et al. 2012).</p>	<p>MIE 957 "Binding, Transthyretin in serum" results in disruption of TH transport , increased free TH in the blood and increased hepatic TH clearance leading to a reduction of T4 in serum and tissues.</p> <p>It is part of: 2 AOPs under development: AOP 152 leading to adverse human neurodevelopmental toxicity, and AOP 366 leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.</p>	Disruption of TH transport may indirectly also affect retinoid levels.	-	Hydroxylated PCB metabolites Hydroxylated PBDE metabolites, phthalates, flavonoids, brominated flame retardants	<p>There are species differences related to the relevance of TTR versus TBG and to function. For example, fish TTR has a higher affinity to T4 (Eales 2019; Eneqvist et al. 2004; Li et al. 2023).</p> <p>High level of confidence for applicability to mammals, moderate for fish. Plausibly applicable to birds, amphibians and reptiles, based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023).</p> <p>Plausibly relevant across all life stages, although TTR levels in serum may vary, e.g. during pregnancy with the lowest levels at 12-14 days of gestation in mice (Cheng et al. 2023). Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
TBG binding	Disruption of TH transport alters TH levels	Use of NETVAL Method 3a for TBG has not been assessed yet.	The MIE 1831 "Binding, Thyroid binding globulin in serum" primarily leading to increased free TH, finally results in decreased THs levels in serum through adaptative increased hepatic clearance.	-	-	Hydroxylated PCB metabolites Hydroxylated PBDE metabolites	<p>Applicable to mammals(Haigis et al. 2023; Foster, Tinwell, and Melching-Kollmuss 2021)</p> <p>There are species differences related to the relevance of TTR versus TBG. Not applicable to any non-mammalian vertebrate. Until now, no TBG protein has been identified in teleost fish (Deal and Volkoff 2020).</p> <p>TBG levels are high in juvenile rats but negligible in adults (Foster, Tinwell, and Melching-Kollmuss 2021).</p>

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
							Plausibly relevant to both sexes
Metabolism and excretion (Block #4)							
Deiodinase (DIO) inhibition							
DIO1 inhibition	Disruption of DIO1 in mice or fish has very mild effects (Walpita, Crawford, and Darras 2010; Schneider et al. 2006)presumably compensated by DIO2, and by thyroid activity in the absence of DIO1, as indicated by simultaneous disruption of DIO1 and DIO2 (Galton et al. 2009; Stinckens et al. 2020)	NETVAL method 4a: I Deiodinase 1 activity based on Sandell-Kolthoff reaction (TM2019-10 (EU)). Under validation. Human and rat deiodinase inhibition assay (DIO 1, 2 and 3) (Kaly-Cell) provided to the OECD TDM EG, for assessment and recommendations on further validation. Human, rat and dog deiodinase inhibition assay (DIO 1, 2 and 3) (Concept Life Sciences). GLP standardization underway.	MIE 1009 "DIO1 inhibition" DIO1 enzyme participates preferably in converting the pro-hormone T4 or rT3 into T3 through outer or inner ring deiodination. Inhibition of DIO1 is expected to decrease the levels of T3, in the serum and tissues. It is part of: 2 WPHA/WNT-endorsed AOPs: AOPs 157 leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation. AOP 158 leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation. 1 AOP under development: AOP 189 leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.		-	6-Propyl-2-thiouracil (PTU). DIO1 sensitivity to PTU appears to vary among species, fish and amphibians being less sensitive than mammals (Darras and Van Herck 2012; Kuiper et al. 2006). Aurothioglucose (ATG)	Moderate confidence level for amphibians. Plausibly applicable to reptiles and birds based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023) In mammals, DIO 1 is thought to control the systemic production of T3 although this assumption has been challenged in humans based on in vitro studies (e.g., (Maia et al. 2011; Maia et al. 2005)). The importance of DIO1 for systemic production of T3 in teleosts has been a controversial issue. Deiodinases catalyze T4 to T3 conversion throughout all life stages. Plausibly relevant to both sexes
DIO2 inhibition	DIO2 knock out in mice and knock down in fish present some phenotypic alteration, such as hearing deficiencies and reduced brain T3 in mice or impaired development, growth and fertility in zebrafish (Hernandez et al.	Human and rat deiodinase inhibition assay (DIO 1, 2 and 3) (Kaly-Cell) provided to the OECD TDM EG, for assessment and recommendations on further validation. Human, rat and dog deiodinase inhibition assay (DIO 1, 2 and 3) (Concept Life Sciences). GLP standardization underway.	MIE 1002 "Inhibition, Deiodinase 2". DIO2 participates in converting T4 into T3 through outer ring deiodination. Thereby, inhibition of DIO2 is expected to decrease the levels of T3. DIO2 can also catalyze rT3 and T2 deiodination. It is part of: 2 WPHA/WNT endorsed AOPs: AOP 155 leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation. AOP 156 leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation. 1 AOP under development: AOP 190		-	Xanthohumol	High level of confidence for the applicability to mammals and fish. Plausibly applicable to amphibians, birds and reptiles, based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023). Deiodinases catalyze T4 to T3 conversion across vertebrates (mammals, fish). While the effects of a lack of DIO1 and/or DIO2 in mice are relatively mild(van der Spek, Fliers, and Boelen

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
	2021; Campos-Barros et al. 2000; Houbrechts et al. 2016), suggesting that DIO2 might be the major 5'-deiodinase.		leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.				2017), DIO2 knockout zebrafish show impaired development, growth and fertility (Houbrechts et al. 2016). In vitro measurements of enzymes activity, combined with model prediction suggest that DIO2 might also have a major contribution to T3 peripheral production in humans (Maia et al. 2005). DIOs catalyze T4 to T3 conversion through all life stages. Plausibly relevant to both sexes
DIO3 inhibition	Inhibiting DIO3 is expected to increase the levels of T3 and T4. Severe phenotypes are associated with knockout (KO) of DIO3 in mice, and knock down in fish, suggesting that DIO3 function is critical (Bagci et al. 2015; Hernandez et al. 2021).	Human and rat deiodinase inhibition assay (DIO 1, 2 and 3) (Kaly-Cell) provided to the OECD TDM EG, for assessment and recommendations on further validation. Human, rat and dog deiodinase inhibition assay (DIO 1, 2 and 3) (Concept Life Sciences). GLP standardization underway.	MIE 1153 "DIO3 inhibition". DIO3 is an inner ring deiodinase that inactivates T4 and T3. Inhibiting DIO3 is thereby expected to increase the levels of T3 and T4. DIO3 KO has been shown to lead to neonatal lethality, impaired fertility, deafness and neurodevelopmental defects in mice (Hernandez et al. 2021). It is part of: 1 AOP under development: AOP 191 Type III iodotyrosine deiodinase (DIO3) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.			Xanthohumol Aurothioglucose (ATG)	High level of confidence for the applicability to fish and amphibians, moderate for mammals. Plausibly applicable to reptiles and birds, based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023) DIOs catalyse T4 to T3 conversion across vertebrates (mammals, fish, amphibians). DIOs catalyze T4 to T3 conversion through all life stages. DIO3 is active particularly in brain and placenta during fetal neurodevelopment to protect fetal neural tissues from high levels of T4 and T3 in maternal blood stream. Plausibly relevant to both sexes
Interference with liver clearance							

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (Intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
Hepatic nuclear receptor activation	Activation of xenobiotic receptors in liver increases activity of metabolic enzymes with consequences on TH serum levels	AhR transactivation assay (CALUX) undergoing ISO validation (Jacobs, Kubickova, and Boshoff 2022).	<p>Activation, Hepatic nuclear receptors, such as PXR or AhR, leads to increase in TH clearance and subsequent decrease in TH levels</p> <p>MIE 1157 “Activation, Hepatic nuclear receptors” is part of AOP 194 leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.</p> <p>MIE 239: “Activation of PXR in liver” is part of the AOP8 leading to adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes in Mammals, including loss of cochlear function. This AOP is open for adoption.</p> <p>MIE 18: “Activation of AhR in liver” is part of: 2 AOPs open for adoption: AOP 458 leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals. AOP 459 leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals. This AOP is open for adoption.</p> <p>No AOPs involving CAR or PPARs with effects on THSD. *</p>	<p>Activation of PXR in liver also leads to increased liver steatosis (AOP 517). This AOP is under development.</p> <p>Activation of AhR in liver also leads to accumulation of lipids (AOP 57), uroporphyrin (AOP 131), or liver fibrosis (AOP 494)</p> <p>AhR activation (MIE 18) is part of many other AOPs not involving the thyroid hormone pathways, but not in liver.</p>	-	<p>PXR: CdCl₂, HgCl₂</p> <p>AhR: TCDD, dioxin-like compounds, PCBs</p>	<p>PXR: High level of confidence for the applicability to mammals, no evidence for applicability to non-mammalian vertebrates (Haigis et al. 2023). Important differences in PXR or CAR transactivation between mammalian species (human, mouse or rat) have been reported in vitro (Paul et al. 2013)).</p> <p>AhR: Moderate level of confidence for the applicability to mammals and fish</p> <p>Plausibly relevant at all life stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
Glucuronidation & sulfation inhibition	<p>Decreased glucuronidation and sulfation activity may increase T4 availability in serum.</p> <p>Both metabolic conjugations regulate the homeostasis of TH in serum.</p>	<p>NETVAL Method 4b: Inhibition of thyroid hormones (THs) glucuronidation using liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC/MS) (TM2019-11 (EU)). Under validation.</p> <p>NETVAL method 4c: Inhibition of thyroid hormones (THs) sulphation using liquid chromatography (TM2019-12 (EU)). Validation stopped - further optimization is needed.</p> <p>UGT Induction assay utilizing LCMS/</p>	<p>MIE 2155 “Inhibition of Sulfotransferase E1 (SULT1E1)” is well described but is not linked to any THSD AOP in the AOP-wiki.*</p> <p>Decreased sulfation affects thyroid hormone homeostasis, and inhibition of UGT activity, caused by decreased AhR gene/protein expression, which may increase T3 and T4 serum levels (Gessner et al. 2012; Yanagiba et al. 2008).</p>	<p>These enzymes also play a role in clearance of other hormones such as estrogens.</p> <p>Inhibition of SULT1E1 (MIE 2155) leads to increased estradiol availability (KE 2251) (AOP 504).</p> <p>Defective sulfation during gestation, may determine an accumulation of xenobiotics in fetus (Wang and James 2006).</p>		<p>Hydroxylated-PCBs, hydroxylated-PAHs, hydroxylated-PBDEs, triclosan, BPA and halogenated BPAs</p>	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant at all life stages. In mammals, sulfoconjugation is particularly important for normal foetal development in the last trimester, facilitating the maternal-foetal exchange of sulfated iodothyronines when this is necessary to provide the necessary amount of T3 to the fetus (Wang and James 2006)</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
		MS (Concept Life Sciences). GLP standardization.					
Glucuronidation & sulfation induction	Increased glucuronidation and sulfation of T4 decreases its availability in serum Both metabolic conjugations regulate the homeostasis of TH in serum.	UGT Induction assay utilizing LC-MS/MS (Concept Life Sciences) is developed to GLP standardization Induction of thyroxine (T4) glucuronidation in primary hepatocytes (Kaly-Cell) was validated "in-house"	KE 295: 'Induction, Upregulation of glucuronyltransferase activity'. This event causes increased T4 clearance from serum thus leading to T4 serum level decrease. It is part of: 3 AOPs under development: AOP 162 leading to thyroid follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas in the rat and mouse. AOP 194 leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis. AOP 458 AhR activation in the liver leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals. This AOP is under development. -1 AOP open for adoption: AOP8 leading to Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals.	These enzymes also play a role in clearance of other hormones such as estrogens.	-	TCDD, dioxin-line compounds, PCBs	Plausibly relevant across vertebrates. Plausibly relevant at all life stages Plausibly relevant to both sexes
Local cellular concentrations (Block #5)							
TH cellular transport / membrane transporter inhibition	Disruption of TH cellular transport	NETVAL Method 5a: Inhibition of monocarboxylate transporter 8 (MCT8) based on Sandell-Kolthoff reaction (TM-2019-13 (EU)). Validation pending. Additional methods for measuring T4 uptake by MCT8, OATP1C1 or OAT4 are being optimized (inventoried in Vergauwen et al. (2024)).	Various transporters exist:-organic anion transporting polypeptides (OATP1C1, OATP1A2, OATP3A1, OATP1A4)-L-type amino acid transporters (LAT1/2) - monocarboxylate transporters (MCT8, MCT10). KE 960: "Increased, Uptake of thyroxine into tissue" KE 1158: "Increased, Hepatic thyroid hormone uptake/transport (amphibian specific)". KE 2258: "Inhibition, monocarboxylate transporter 8 (MCT8)" This event will lead to altered cell TH membrane transport and affects TH levels in the tissue. This is tissue specific (Noyes et al. 2019). In the brain, it affects cognition and motor function. <i>Brain</i> KE 960 is part of	DIO2 and DIO3 enzyme activity are also involved in T3/T4 levels in the brain. If transport decreases, enzyme activity might be decreased.	Disruption of TH levels in the brain can cause heterotopia <i>in vivo</i> .	Silycristin (MCT8 inhibitor), lesinurad (OATP transport inhibitor) 2-Amino-2-norbornanecarboxylic acid (BCH) (LAT1 and LAT2 inhibitor) and TBBPA (OATP1C1 inhibitor) (Chen et al. 2023; Wagenaars et al. 2024a; Wagenaars et al. 2024b; Wagenaars et al. 2025).	Plausibly relevant across vertebrates Changes in transport in the various tissues throughout development might lead to different outcomes. Plausibly relevant to both sexes

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
			<p>AOP 152: "Interference with thyroid serum binding protein transthyretin and subsequent adverse human neurodevelopmental toxicity." This AOP is under development.</p> <p><i>Liver:</i> KE 1158: is part of: AOP 367: "Binding to thyroid binding globulin in serum leads to altered amphibian metamorphosis." This AOP is under development.</p>				
Cellular responses (Block #6)							
THR agonism	<p>Activation of THRα/β impacts on the transcription of target genes.</p> <p>THRα and THRβ are highly selective, and a limited number of environmental chemicals is known to agonistically bind the THRα and THRβ.</p>	<p><i>Xenopus</i> Eleutheroembryonic Thyroid Assay (XETA) (OECD TG 248)</p> <p>NETVAL Method 6a: Human thyroid hormone receptor alpha (TRα) and Human thyroid hormone receptor beta (TRβ) reporter gene transactivation measuring agonist activities (TM2019-14 (EU)). Validation ongoing – recommended to include antagonism.</p> <p>NETVAL Method 6b: CALUX human thyroid hormone receptor beta (TRβ) reporter gene transactivation measuring agonist and antagonist activities (TM2019-15 (EU)). Validation ongoing.</p> <p>NETVAL Method 8a: T-screen assay - Measurement of proliferation of rat pituitary-derived cell</p>	<p>THR agonism as well as hyperthyroidism have received less attention compared to THR antagonism and hypothyroidism. THR agonists have mainly been investigated in a pharmaceutical context based on their potential to restore thyroid status in various thyroid disorders and help alleviate metabolic disorders such as obesity (Polini et al. 2025; Rehman et al. 2023).</p> <p>MIE 2216 "Binding of antagonist to thyroid hormone receptor" MIE 1656 "Antagonism, Thyroid Receptor." There are two major thyroid hormone receptor subtypes: thyroid hormone receptor alpha (THRα) and beta (THRβ). Chemicals antagonizing THRα decrease transcription of target genes. MIE 1656 is part of 2 AOPs under development: AOP 300: "TR Antagonism and DNT." AOP 485 "TR antagonism leading to decreased cognition." MIE 2216 is part of 1 AOP under development: AOP 525: "Leading to impaired learning and memory through reduced oligodendrocyte</p>	THR α and THR β are known to cross-talk with RXRs, ERs, PPARs, AR, GR, MR, PR, VDR and LXR (Liu and Brent 2010; Ren and Zhu 2022).	-	<p>Natural ligands T3 and T4</p> <p>Sobetirome</p> <p>Tetraiodothyroacetic acid (TETRAC)</p>	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates</p> <p>Plausibly relevant at all life stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
THR antagonism	<p>Inhibition of THRα/β impacts on the transcription of target genes.</p> <p>THRα and THRβ are highly selective, and a limited number of environmental chemicals is known to antagonistically bind the THRα and THRβ.</p>	<p>validation ongoing – recommended to include antagonism.</p> <p>NETVAL Method 6b: CALUX human thyroid hormone receptor beta (TRβ) reporter gene transactivation measuring agonist and antagonist activities (TM2019-15 (EU)). Validation ongoing.</p> <p>NETVAL Method 8a: T-screen assay - Measurement of proliferation of rat pituitary-derived cell</p>	<p>MIE 2216 "Binding of antagonist to thyroid hormone receptor" MIE 1656 "Antagonism, Thyroid Receptor." There are two major thyroid hormone receptor subtypes: thyroid hormone receptor alpha (THRα) and beta (THRβ). Chemicals antagonizing THRα decrease transcription of target genes. MIE 1656 is part of 2 AOPs under development: AOP 300: "TR Antagonism and DNT." AOP 485 "TR antagonism leading to decreased cognition." MIE 2216 is part of 1 AOP under development: AOP 525: "Leading to impaired learning and memory through reduced oligodendrocyte</p>	THR α and THR β are known to cross-talk with RXRs, ERs, PPARs, AR, GR, MR, PR, VDR and LXR (Liu and Brent 2010; Ren and Zhu 2022).	-	<p>Mostly drugs or drug candidates (e.g. 1-850 (Schapira et al. 2003))</p> <p>TBBPA (OECD 2014; Kitamura et al. 2005; Levy-Bimbot et al. 2012)</p> <p>NH-3 (CAS447415-26-1) (Grover et al. 2007; Walter et al. 2021)</p>	<p>High level of confidence for the applicability to mammals, amphibians and fish. Plausibly applicable to reptiles and birds, based on SeqAPASS (Haigis et al. 2023)</p> <p>Plausibly relevant during development and at adulthood</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>

Mechanism / effect component	Relevance of mechanism/ effect component	Key assays/TGs addressing the mechanism/effect component	Main relevant pathways linking to the mechanism/effect component (AOPs and/or other evidence)	Related pathways / cross-interactions (intra-/inter-network)	Morphological alteration at the cell/tissue level (especially those available from in vivo tests)	Prototypical substances associated with the mechanism/ effect component	Biological domain of applicability (taxonomic, life stage, sex)
		line GH3 indicates the presence of of THR (ant)agonists (TM2019-17 (EU)). Validation ongoing.	differentiation during neurodevelopment."				
TH-SPECIFIC KEY EVENTS							
Thyroid gland weight increase and histopathological changes	Indication of altered thyroid gland/ follicle activity, mainly as a compensatory response to decreased TH levels (via increasing TSH)	<p>Several in vivo assays at various levels of validation include thyroid histopathology (mainly follicular cell height increase and colloid area decrease) and/or thyroid gland weight measurements: TGs in rodents: OECD TGs 407, 408, 409, 414, 416, 421, 422, 443, 451, 452, 453, US EPA 890.1450, US EPA 890.1500.</p> <p>TGs in amphibians: OECD TG 241.</p> <p>TGs in birds: US EPA 890.2100</p> <p>Guidance for Thyroid Assays in Pregnant Animals, Fetuses and Postnatal Animals, and Adult Animals (Comparative Thyroid Assay (CTA)). Well-established, validated in practice.</p> <p>In fish, the following assays are undergoing validation: THSD Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (tFET) test and THSD Fish Early Life Stage (tFELS) test.</p> <p>The integrated Fish Endocrine Disruption Test (iFEDT), combining OECD TGs 229 & 234, includes</p>	<p>KE739 "Increased hypertrophy and proliferation". Increased thyroid gland weight and hyperplasia/hypertrophy occur as a compensatory response to decreased TH levels, based on reduced negative feedback at the level of the hypothalamus and pituitary and resulting in increased secretion of TRH and TSH. It is usually not a causal event leading to the adverse health effect, except in the case of thyroid adenoma/carcinoma observed only in rodents.</p> <p>KE739 is part of: 3 AOPs under development leading to thyroid follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas in the rat and mouse:</p> <p>AOP 162: Initiated by enhanced hepatic clearance of thyroid hormones.</p> <p>AOP 110: Initiated by inhibition of iodide pump activity</p> <p>AOP 119: Initiated by inhibition of thyroid peroxidase.</p>	Estrogens may have a role in the promotion of proliferation of thyroid cells (Santin and Furlanetto 2011; Zane et al. 2014).	Histopathological changes in the thyroid follicles <i>in vivo</i>	6-propylthiouracil, methimazole, perchlorate, amitrole, 3-nitro-L-tyrosine	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates. Species-related differences can occur, e.g., due to different sensitivity to TSH stimulation</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to all life stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes. In humans, women are known to have a higher prevalence of thyroid hypo- or hyperfunction (hyperthyroidism mostly occurs during pregnancy) than men, which is related to estrogens.</p>

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		thyroid histopathology (Gölz et al. 2024b; Pannetier et al. 2024). Validation foreseen in the near future but not planned yet.					
Decreased serum/tissue T4 levels	Both decrease and increase in T4 and T3 (T3 being the more active) are diagnostic for assessing THSD modalities. These are central key events resulting from multiple MIEs and leading to several adverse outcomes.	<p><i>Xenopus</i> Eleutheroembryonic Thyroid Assay (XETA) (OECD TG 248).</p> <p>Assessment of T4 and T3 levels in serum is required in the OECD TGs 408 and 414 and recommended in OECD TG 407, 452 and 453. Assessment of T4 is required in the OECD TGs 421, 422, and 443.</p> <p>Pubertal Development and thyroid function in intact juvenile / Peripubertal male and female rats assay (US EPA 890.1450, US EPA 890.1500).</p> <p>Guidance for Thyroid Assays in Pregnant Animals, Fetuses and Postnatal Animals, and Adult Animals (Comparative Thyroid Assay (CTA)). Well-established, validated in practice.</p> <p>THSD Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (tFET) test and THSD Fish Early Life Stage (tFELS) test (ERGO project). Validation ongoing.</p> <p>The integrated Fish Endocrine Disruption</p>	<p>KE 281 "Thyroxine (T4) in serum, decreased"</p> <p>KE280: "Thyroxine (T4) in neuronal tissue, Decreased"</p> <p>Both KEs are part of: 2 WPHA/WNT Endorsed AOPs: AOPs 42: "Inhibition of Thyroperoxidase and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals" AOP 54: "Inhibition of Na+/I-symporter (NIS) leads to learning and memory impairment."</p> <p>5 AOPs under development: AOP 65: "Inhibition of NIS and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." AOP 134: "NIS Inhibition and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals)." AOP 152: "Interference with thyroid serum binding protein transthyretin and subsequent adverse human neurodevelopmental toxicity". AOP 458: "AhR activation in the liver leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." AOP 459: "AhR activation in the thyroid leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals."</p> <p>1 AOP open for adoption: AOP 8: "Upregulation of Thyroid Hormone Catabolism via Activation of Hepatic Nuclear Receptors, and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." KE 281 is also part of another: 1 WPHA/WNT-endorsed AOP:</p>	Indirect linkage with pathways initiated through hepatic nuclear receptors such as AhR (Nugegoda and Kibria 2017; McKinney et al. 1985; Brown et al. 2004); interaction with steroid pathway (Liu et al. 2011)	Histopathological changes in the thyroid follicles in vivo as a result of compensatory responses to decreased TH levels	6-propylthiouracil, methimazole, Mercaptobenzothiazole Halogenated phenols, PCBs, PBDEs, Phthalates, PFAS potassium perchlorate, potassium thiocyanate, sodium bromide, benzophenone-2, resorcinol, phloroglucinol, amitrole, ethylene thiourea, genistein (Raldua and Babin 2009; Thienpont et al. 2011), 3-nitro-L-tyrosine (Olker et al. 2018).	Plausibly relevant across vertebrates but there are some uncertainties related to the sensitivity differences between species. Plausibly relevant at all life stages Plausibly relevant to both sexes (limited information available for fish).

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		<p>Test (iFEDT), combining OECD TGs 229 & 234, recommends measuring T3 and T4 in zebrafish homogenates, and describes T4 measurement using ELISA kit (Gözl et al. 2024b; Pannetier et al. 2024). Validation foreseen in the near future but not planned yet.</p> <p>NETVAL Method 7a: Measurement of intrafollicular thyroxine (T4) using Zebrafish Eleutheroembryo Thyroid Assay (ZETA) (TM2019-16 (EU)). Validation ongoing.</p> <p>Human Thyroid Microtissue test method (US-EPA). Validation ongoing.</p> <p>Although THs measurement is included in several TGs, the methods are often not provided. Here are possible methods available: Free THs can be measured through equilibrium dialysis and ultrafiltration (Midgley 2001) combining RIA to measure total TH and dialysis to estimate the free fraction (Zoeller, Tyl, and Tan 2007) . LC-MS/MS (Pannetier et al. 2023), ELISA</p>	<p>AOP 159 leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation in fish). 1 AOP under review: AOP 363: “Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered retinal layer structure.” 14 AOPs under development: AOP 175 “Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.” AOP 176 “Sodium Iodide Symporter (NIS) Inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.” AOP 194: “Hepatic nuclear receptor activation leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.” AOP 366: “Competitive binding to thyroid hormone carrier protein transthyretin (TTR) leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.” AOP 367: “Competitive binding to thyroid hormone carrier protein thyroid binding globulin (TBG) leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.” AOP 364: “Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via decreased eye size.” AOP 365: “Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered photoreceptor patterning.” AOP 119: “Inhibition of thyroid peroxidase leading to follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas (in rat and mouse).” AOP 110: “Inhibition of iodide pump activity leading to follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas (in rat and mouse).” AOP 162: Enhanced hepatic clearance of thyroid hormones leading to thyroid follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas in the rat and mouse.” AOP 128 “Kidney dysfunction by decreased thyroid hormone.” AOP 188 “Iodotyrosine deiodinase (IYD) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p>				

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		(Rodrigues et al. 2022; Chang et al. 2012), RIA (van der Ven et al. 2006) or CLIA can also be used. Extracted materials can also be quantified by HPLC, and Immunohistochemistry (IHC) for tissue T4.	<p>AOP 192 "Pendrin inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis." AOP 193: "Dual oxidase (DUOX) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis." AOP 457: "Succinate dehydrogenase inhibition leading to increased insulin resistance through reduction in circulating thyroxine."</p>				
Increased serum/tissue T4 levels			<p>KE 959 "Increased, Free serum thyroxine" (T4) is part of: 3 AOPs under development: AOP 152: "Interference with thyroid serum binding protein transthyretin and subsequent adverse human neurodevelopmental toxicity." AOP 367: in which binding to thyroid binding globulin in serum leads to altered amphibian metamorphosis. AOP 366: "Competitive binding to thyroid hormone carrier protein transthyretin (TTR) leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis."</p>			PCBs and PBDEs	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant at all life stages: essential for fetal development and brain growth, influencing growth in childhood, regulating metabolism and reproductive health in adulthood, and impacting aging, metabolism, and cognitive function in old age. Critical for metamorphosis in amphibians.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes. Genetic predispositions to thyroid conditions affect SHBG and testosterone levels, with fT4 associated with increased testosterone and estradiol in women only (Kjaergaard et al. 2021). Genetic influences on TSH and fT4 levels are more prominent in females than in males, indicating stronger genetic impacts on thyroid function in females (Lee et al. 2018).</p>
Decreased serum/tissue T3 levels			<p>KE 1003 "Decreased, Triiodothyronine" (T3) is part of: 5 WPHA/WNT-endorsed AOP: AOP 155: "Deiodinase 2 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation."</p>	Interaction with steroid pathway (Liu et al. 2011)	Histopathological changes in the thyroid follicles in vivo as a result of compensatory responses to decreased TH levels	6-propylthiouracil, methimazole, iopanoic acid, 3-nitro-L-tyrosine	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates with some uncertainties related to species sensitivity</p> <p>Plausibly relevant across different life stages but expected to have highest</p>

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			<p>AOP 156: "Deiodinase 2 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>AOP 157:"Deiodinase 1 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>AOP 158:"Deiodinase 1 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>AOP 159:"Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>1 AOP under review: AOP 363 "Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered retinal layer structure." 3 AOPs under development: AOP 189: "Type I iodothyronine deiodinase(DIO1) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis." AOP 364: "Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via decreased eye size." AOP 365:"Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered photoreceptor patterning."</p>				<p>sensitivity during development</p> <p>Relevant to both sexes but sensitivity might differ</p>
Increased serum/tissue T3 levels			<p>KE 1154 "Increased, Triiodothyronine (T3) in tissues " is part of AOP 191 "Type III iodotyrosine deiodinase (DIO3) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis"</p> <p>Increase in T3 characterizes thyrotoxicosis, which is associated with various symptoms, such as hyperactivity, anxiety, weight loss or cardiac arrhythmias in humans.</p>			Some chemicals have been associated with increased T3 serum levels (e.g., TDCIPP) but we could not find evidence for a prototypical stressor with a defined MoA.	<p>Plausibly relevant across several vertebrate classes (mammals, fish, amphibians)</p> <p>Plausibly relevant at all life stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
Altered TSH levels	Increased TSH levels stimulate TH synthesis and proliferation of the thyroid follicles.	Assessment of TSH levels in serum is recommended in the OECD TGs 421 and 422 (T4 and TSH preferably be measured as "total"), 407 , 452 , 453 .	KE1023 "Increased, Thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH)". TH levels are regulated, not only at the plasma level, but also at the individual cell level, to maintain homeostasis. This is succeeded by the efficient regulatory mechanism of the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis			aminotriazole and propylthiouracil (Akane et al. 2022)	In general, significant variation in TSH reference intervals is influenced by age, sex, and ethnicity (Ehrenkranz et al. 2015). For instance, TSH and the prevalence of antithyroid antibodies

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		<p>And required in OECD TGs 443, 414, 408. Guidance for Thyroid Assays in Pregnant Animals, Fetuses and Postnatal Animals, and Adult Animalsm (Comparative Thyroid Assay (CTA)). Well-established, validated in practice.</p> <p>Pubertal Development and thyroid function in intact juvenile/ Peripubertal male and female rats assay (US EPA 890.1450, US EPA 890.1500).</p> <p>Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA); Chemiluminescent Immunoassay (CLIA); Radioimmunoassay (RIA); Immunofluorometric Assay (IFMA); Third-Generation Assays (Ultra-Sensitive TSH Assays)</p>	<p>with hypothalamic secretion of the thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) and subsequent secretion of thyrotropin (TSH) by the pituitary.</p> <p>KE1023 is part of AOP: 4 AOPs under development: AOP 110 "Inhibition of iodide pump activity leading to follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas (in rat and mouse)" AOP 119 leading to thyroid carcinoma in rodents. AOP 162: "Enhanced hepatic clearance of thyroid hormones leading to thyroid follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas in the rat and mouse." AOP 190: "Type II iodothyronine deiodinase (DIO2) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis."</p>				<p>are greater in females, increase with age, and are greater in whites and Mexican Americans than in blacks (Hollowell et al. 2002).</p> <p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates, including fish, and amphibians</p> <p>Plausibly relevant across all life stages. At birth, there is a surge in TRH and TSH levels, known as the "neonatal TSH surge," which stimulates the newborn's thyroid gland to produce THs. This surge is essential for thermogenesis and adaptation to the extrauterine environment. (Buyukgebiz 2013; Kaluarachchi et al. 2017). Aging affects the HPT axis, with changes in TRH and TSH secretion patterns- There may be a decrease in thyroid hormone levels (Gauthier et al. 2020).</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes.</p>
DOWNSTREAM KEY EVENTS							
Altered hippocampal anatomy / morphology of the hippocampal gene expression or physiology altered.	Altered brain development / morphology of the hippocampal anatomy due to a change in TH levels in the brain	Basic histology is performed in the OECD TG 426 and 443 that includes DNT endpoints. Alteration in hippocampal anatomy will be measured but subtle changes are not included such as synaptogenesis, hypomyelination, heterotopia, neuronal network formation and neuronal anatomy.	<p>KE 757 'hippocampal anatomy altered' results from a decrease in brain T4 levels in various AOPs.</p> <p>KE 757 is part of: 1 WPHA/WNT Endorsed AOP: AOP 42 "Inhibition of Thyroperoxidase and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." 3 AOPs under development: AOP 134: "NIS Inhibition and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals)."</p>	AOP 442 Binding to voltage gate sodium channels during development leads to cognitive impairment. This AOP is under review.	Altered hippocampal anatomy is tested <i>in vivo</i>		<p>Plausibly relevant to mammals (anatomy of other species are quite different)</p> <p>Relevant during critical windows of brain development in fetal and early postnatal stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>

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		This endpoint can be tested <i>in vivo</i> with a variety of standard biochemical, molecular, cellular, histological and anatomical methods including cellular staining and immunohistochemistry including microscopy.	<p>AOP 152: "Interference with thyroid serum binding protein transthyretin and subsequent adverse human neurodevelopmental toxicity." AOP 300: "Thyroid Receptor Antagonism and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." 1 AOP open for adoption: AOP8: "Upregulation of Thyroid Hormone Catabolism via Activation of Hepatic Nuclear Receptors, and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals."</p> <p>Other related Key events KE 756 'Hippocampal gene expression, Altered' and KE 758 'Hippocampal Physiology', Altered are part of: AOP 458: "AhR activation in the liver leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals" AOP 459 "AhR activation in the thyroid leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals."</p>				
Level of BDNF reduced	BDNF is used as a biomarker of effect for neurodevelopmental defects.	<p>Not included in in vitro or in vivo assays that are validated or ready for/under validation at this point.*</p> <p>There are several commercial double antibody sandwich ELISA kits that can be used for identification of BDNF levels in biological fluids (Trajkovska et al. 2007). Western blotting, immunochemistry and immunofluorescence can also be used.</p>	<p>KE 381 "Reduced levels of BDNF" is part of the WPHA/WNT Endorsed AOP 54 "Inhibition of Na⁺/I⁻ symporter (NIS) leads to learning and memory impairment."</p>	Antagonism of N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) and subsequent decrease in calcium influx may also affect BDNF levels (AOPs 12 & 13)		BPA TBBPA	<p>Plausibly relevant to mammals</p> <p>Relevant during brain development</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>

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Decreased synaptogenesis	Synaptogenesis is crucial for normal brain functioning	Not included in in vitro or in vivo assays that are validated or ready for/under validation at this point.*	<p>KE 385 "Decrease of synaptogenesis." Decreased synaptogenesis affects the connections and communication between neurons and is involved in network formation</p> <p>KE 385 is part of the WPHA/WNT endorsed AOP: AOP 54 linking NIS inhibition to learning and memory impairment.</p>	<p>Decreased synaptogenesis also results from other mechanisms, such as antagonism of N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) (AOP 13 - WPHA/WNT endorsed) or Retinoic Acid receptor (RAR) antagonism (AOP 533 – under development):</p> <p>AOP 13 linking NMDARs antagonism to impaired learning and memory abilities. AOP 533: linking RAR antagonism to impaired learning and memory.</p>	Might affect tissue morphology		<p>Plausibly relevant to mammals.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant across all life stages.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
Hypomyelination	Myelination is crucial for normal brain functioning	Not included in well-established, validated or under validation assays at this point.*	<p>KE 2107 'Hypomyelination'. Decreased myelination leads to a decrease in neural network formation and the formation of white matter.</p> <p>KE 2107 is part of: 2 AOPs under development involving THSD :</p> <p>AOP 458: "AhR activation in the liver leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." . AOP 525: "Reduced oligodendrocyte differentiation during neurodevelopment leading to impaired learning and memory."</p>	Hypomyelination as KE is also included in AOPs 487, 488 and 489 (all under development) with different MIEs (altered cholesterol metabolism, increased ROS, altered binding to VGSC), all leading to decreased cognitive function.	Hypomyelination could be observed in in vivo tests, but this is currently not included.		<p>Plausibly relevant to mammals and fish.</p> <p>Relevant during brain development.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
Heterotopia	<p>We distinguish periventricular heterotopia, and Subcortical band heterotopia (SBH)</p> <p>Periventricular heterotopia is a neurodevelopmental defect in several species, often associated with seizure. It is observed in hypothyroid rats, and forms consistently and</p>	<p>Not included in in vitro or in vivo assays that are validated or ready for/under validation at this point.*</p> <p>Histological examination of brain sections (throughout the hippocampus) with neuronal staining (e.g., NeuN antibody) at postnatal stages.</p>	<p>AO 2095: 'Periventricular heterotopia formation'. Some hypotheses have been formulated to explain a TH-mediated heterotopia (Gilbert et al. 2014). For example, TH-mediated gene regulation might directly impact neuronal migration and/or apoptosis of misplaced neurons. THs might also act indirectly, e.g., by affecting brain vasculature which is used as a scaffold for proper migration. However, solid evidence to verify these hypotheses is lacking.</p> <p>AO 2095 is part of: AOP 402 "Thyroid peroxidase (TPO) inhibition leads to periventricular</p>		Clusters of misplaced neurons in the corpus callosum.	PTU	<p>So far, only observed in rats. Not observed in mice or non-mammalian vertebrates.</p> <p>Relevant during developmental stages.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes.</p>

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	dose-dependently following TPO inhibition in rats (Gilbert et al. 2014), but not in mice (Ramhoj et al. 2023).		heterotopia formation in the developing rat brain." (currently no KERs have been included in this AOP).				
Impaired eye development	Impaired eye development leads to visual dysfunction which is relevant both to humans and wildlife	tFET and tFELS tests (part of OECD project 2.64 and currently under pre-validation) include histopathological analysis of retinal layers, iFEDT	<p>KE 1877 "Altered, retinal layer structure"</p> <p>KE 1878 "Decreased, eye size"</p> <p>KE 1640 "Altered, photoreceptor patterning". THSD is known to cause reduced eye size, altered retinal layer structure and altered photoreceptor patterning.</p> <p>KE 1877 is part of: 1 AOP under review: AOP 363 "Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered retinal layer structure."</p> <p>KE 1878 is part of: 1 AOP under development: AOP 364: "Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via decreased eye size." KE 1640 is part of: 1 AOP under development: AOP 365: "Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered photoreceptor patterning."</p>	RAR/RXR, ER signaling	Retinal histopathological changes and eye size may be assessed in several in vivo assays across vertebrates.	6-propylthiouracil, iopanoic acid, perchlorate	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates since eye structure and the role of THs in its development is highly conserved.</p> <p>Most knowledge available during the embryonic period. Knowledge gap related to effects on eyes of developed organisms.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes, but potential differences in sensitivity are unclear.</p>
Impaired swim bladder inflation	Impaired swim bladder inflation in fish leads to reduced swimming performance which reduces survival	tFET and tFELS tests (part of OECD project 2.64 and currently under pre-validation) include assessment of swim bladder inflation, iFEDT	<p>KE 1004 "Reduced, Posterior swim bladder inflation" (relevant to the embryonic stage in fish species with two swim bladder chambers) is a consequence of decreased T3 levels and leads to reduced swimming performance.</p> <p>KE 1004 is part of: 2 WPHA/WNT endorsed AOPs: AOP 155 "Deiodinase 2 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation."</p>	Multiple mechanisms (including non-ED) lead to impaired swim bladder inflation.	Assessment of swim bladder inflation is currently being added to the FET (TG 236) and the FELS (TG 210) test and may be added to other fish TGs (e.g., TG 234) in the future.	6-propylthiouracil, iopanoic acid, methimazole	<p>Plausibly relevant across fish species with swim bladders.</p> <p>For species with two swim bladder chambers (e.g., zebrafish, fathead minnow), posterior chamber inflation occurring during early development is less responsive to inhibition of TH synthesis compared to anterior chamber inflation occurring during</p>

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			<p>AOP 157 "Deiodinase 1 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>KE 1007 is part of: 3 WPHA/WNT endorsed AOPs: AOP 156 Deiodinase 2 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation. AOP 158 Deiodinase 1 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation. AOP 159. Thyroperoxidase inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation.</p>				<p>late larval development. The unique swim bladder of Medaka inflates during larval development.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes. In zebrafish and fathead minnow, posterior chamber inflation occurs before gonad differentiation and anterior chamber inflation occurs during the initial stages of gonad differentiation. In medaka, sex can be morphologically distinguished as soon as 10 days post fertilization and females appear more susceptible to THSD-induced swim bladder dysfunction than males (Godfrey et al. 2019).</p>

ADVERSE OUTCOMES

Cognitive, learning, memory deficits	THs are critical for normal nervous system development. Decrease in TH levels impair the development of the hippocampus which plays a major role in cognition and learning and memory	<p>Developmental Neurotoxicity Study (OECD TG 426), including learning and memory tests on pups, pre- and post-weaning.</p> <p>Extended one-generation reproductive toxicity study (OECD TG 443).</p> <p>The US EPA and OECD Developmental Neurotoxicity (DNT) Guidelines (OCSP 870.6300 or OECD 426) both require testing of learning and memory. These DNT Guidelines have been deemed valid to identify developmental neurotoxicity and</p>	<p>AO 402 "Cognitive function decrease" is an Adverse Outcome in several AOPs with decrease in T4 serum and in neuronal tissue:</p> <p>AO 402 is part of: 1 WPHA/WNT Endorsed AOP: AOP 42 "Inhibition of Thyroperoxidase and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals."</p> <p>7 AOPs under development: AOP 65 "Inhibition of NIS and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." AOP 134 "NIS Inhibition and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." AOP 152 "Interference with thyroid serum binding protein transthyretin</p>	Cognition decrease can be induced also by other mechanisms relevant for brain development such as: -inhibition of Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) (MIE 12; AOP 405, no status description) -binding to laminin (MIE 2109; AOP 486, no status description) -alteration of cholesterol metabolism (KE 2115, no MIE; AOP 487) -increased ROS production (MIE 257; AOP 488, no status description) -Binding to voltage-gated sodium channel (MIE 1353; AOP 489, no status description)	In vivo endpoints are lacking for cognitive function and learning and memory.	<p>propylthiouracil, methimazole</p> <p>Organophosphates</p> <p>TBBPA</p>	<p>Plausibly relevant across mammals and likely to be applicable to other classes of vertebrates where TH drive development of the nervous system (e.g., birds, fish, reptiles).</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to fetal and early postnatal ages during critical windows of nervous system development where TH guide normal development of the brain.</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes; there are no data to suggest sex differences in susceptibility to TH disruption during development.</p>
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		<p>adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes (Makris et al. 2009).</p> <p>Various standardized learning and memory tests have been developed for human neuropsychological testing.</p> <p>In rodents several methods are well established to evaluate the effects of developmental thyroid disruption such as radial arm maze (RAM), the Barnes maze, the Morris water maze (MWM), test of novel object recognition, and fear among others.</p>	<p>and subsequent adverse human neurodevelopmental toxicity".</p> <p>AOP 300: "TR Antagonism and DNT."</p> <p>AOP 485 "TR antagonism leading to decreased cognition."</p> <p>AOP 458: "AhR activation in the liver leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals."</p> <p>AOP 459 "AhR activation in the thyroid leading to Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals."</p>				
Loss of cochlear function	<p>Hearing impairment can severely impact quality-of-life in humans and survival in animals.</p> <p>Hypothyroidism has however been associated with sudden sensorineural hearing loss (SSNHL) during later life (Kim et al. 2020).</p>	<p>Not included in in vitro or in vivo assays that are validated or ready for/under validation at this point.*</p>	<p>KE 319 "Loss, cochlear function" is part of:</p> <p>AOP 8 "Upregulation of Thyroid Hormone Catabolism via Activation of Hepatic Nuclear Receptors, and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals." This AOP is open for adoption.</p>			PCBs, PTU	<p>The inner ear of vertebrates has presumably emerged from a common ancestor through divergent development (Warchol 2011). While some structures are unique to certain taxonomic groups, such as the cochlea (found in mammals, birds and reptiles), some are also shared across taxonomic groups like the sensory epithelium in the inner ear (comprised of hair cells and supporting cells) or the saccular macula (Warchol 2011; Basch et al. 2016) which could be impacted by a common THSD mechanism.</p>

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							<p>Cochlear development during postnatal development is a critical period in mammals (Crofton et al. 2000). Impaired auditory development may be unlikely in humans due to limited THSD during the critical period of development. Non-mammalian vertebrates appear to regenerate hair cells as adults (Warchol 2011).</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes.</p>
Visual dysfunction	Visual dysfunction adversely affects health in humans, and survival in wildlife	<p>Not included in in vitro or in vivo assays that are validated or ready for/under validation at this point.*</p> <p>Visual dysfunction can be assessed using specific behavioral assays Potential methods for use across vertebrates include, e.g., electroretinograms, visual evoked potentials and optomotor/optokinetic response assays.</p>	<p>KE 1643 "Altered, visual function" is a result of KE 1877 "Altered, retinal layer structure".</p> <p>The involvement of THs in visual system development is supported by publications across different vertebrate taxa (summarized in Gözl et al. 2022; Haigis et al. 2023) and multiple studies reported visual dysfunction as a result of THSD (Besson et al. 2020; Dehnert, Karasov, and Wolman 2019; Flamarique 2013; Boyes et al. 2018; Mirabella et al. 2005).</p> <p>KE 1643 and KE 1877 are part of: 1 AOP under review: AOP 363 "Thyropoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered retinal layer structure." 2 AOPs under development: AOP 364 "Thyropoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via decreased eye size." AOP 365 "Thyropoxidase inhibition leading to altered visual function via altered photoreceptor patterning."</p>	<p>RAR/RXR, ER signaling</p> <p>AOP 297: Inhibition of retinaldehyde dehydrogenase leads to population decline AOP 399 Inhibition of Src family tyrosine kinase A (Fyna) leading to increased mortality via decreased eye size (Microphthalmos).</p>		<p>6-propylthiouracil, methimazole, potassium perchlorate, iopanoic acid</p>	<p>Plausibly relevant across vertebrates (mammals, fish, amphibians, birds) because structure and functionality of the visual system are well conserved (reviewed by Lamb, Collin, and Pugh (2007))</p> <p>Plausibly relevant mostly at early life stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>
Thyroid follicular tumors	Occurrence of thyroid follicular adenomas/carcinomas impairs	Rodent in vivo TGs including thyroid weight and histopathology can	AO 741 "Increase, Adenomas/carcinomas (follicular cell)".	Evidence for the role of estrogen in thyroid cancer development is contradictory and observed in human cells,	Increased thyroid weight, follicular cell hyperplasia	Phenobarbital, Pyrethroids	Plausibly relevant to rodents. The relation between THSD and thyroid tumors seems to

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	thyroid functionality	pick up thyroid follicular tumors: OECD TGs 407, 408, 409, 414, 416, 421, 422, 443, 451, 452, 453, US EPA 890.1450, US EPA 890.1500. Guidance for Thyroid Assays in Pregnant Animals, Fetuses and Postnatal Animals, and Adult Animalsm (Comparative Thyroid Assay (CTA)). Well-established, validated in practice.	AO 741 is part of AOP: 3 AOPs under development: AOP 110 "Inhibition of iodide pump activity leading to follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas (in rat and mouse)" AOP 119 "Inhibition of thyroid peroxidase leading to follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas (in rat and mouse)." AOP 162 "Enhanced hepatic clearance of thyroid hormones leading to thyroid follicular cell adenomas and carcinomas in the rat and mouse."	with a different mechanism involving ERs or GPER (Kumar, Klinge, and Goldstein 2010; Zhang et al. 2017).	and cell hypertrophy		be of lower relevance to humans (Bartsch et al. 2018). While thyroid gland hyperplasia/ hypertrophy has been observed in different species, the induction of follicular tumors through THSD has only been observed in rodents. Data in non-mammalian vertebrates are missing. Plausibly relevant to adults Plausibly relevant to both sexes, but incidence is generally higher in male compared to female rats (Hurley 1998).
Impaired metamorphosis	Delayed amphibian metamorphosis may lead to issues with food availability, leaving the water in time for seasonal effects like pond-drying (Laurila and Kujasalo 1999) etc. and may impact the survival of individuals and status of populations	Amphibian Metamorphosis Assay (AMA) OECD TG 231 Larval Amphibian Growth and Development Assay (LAGDA) OECD TG 241 Extended Amphibian Metamorphosis Assay (EAMA) (Ortego et al. 2021)	KE 1101 "Altered, amphibian metamorphosis" Amphibian metamorphosis is a prototypical TH-dependent biological process. Metamorphosis requires a specifically timed TH surge and is delayed by mechanisms decreasing TH levels or accelerated by TR agonists (Kamel et al. 2022). Metamorphosis includes limb emergence and development, lung development, gill and tail resorption, gut remodeling, metabolic profile changes in the liver, skin keratinization, etc. KE 1101 is part of: 11 AOPs under development: AOP 175 "Thyropoxidase inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis." AOP 176 "Sodium Iodide Symporter (NIS) Inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis." AOP 188 "Iodotyrosine deiodinase (IYD) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis." AOP 189 "Type I iodothyronine deiodinase (DIO1) inhibition leading		Amphibian metamorphosis is observed morphologically in two OECD in vivo tests – OECD TG 231 and OECD TG 241	methimazole, 6-propylthiouracil, loproanoic acid	Plausibly relevant to all amphibian species Plausibly relevant during a specific developmental phase. Plausibly relevant to both sexes

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			<p>to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 190 “Type II iodothyronine deiodinase (DIO2) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 191 “Type III iodothyronine deiodinase (DIO3) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 192 “Pendrin inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 193 “Dual oxidase (DUOX) inhibition leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 194: “Hepatic nuclear receptor activation leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 366: “Competitive binding to thyroid hormone carrier protein transthyretin (TTR) leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p> <p>AOP 367: “Competitive binding to thyroid hormone carrier protein thyroid binding globulin (TBG) leading to altered amphibian metamorphosis.”</p>				
Impaired swimming	Impaired swimming performance reduces the population growth rate, which is important for environmental health.	<p>At present not included in validated TGs but routinely measured in early life stage as well as adult fish in the literature (Horie et al. 2023; Stinckens et al. 2020)</p> <p>Swimming performance could be added as an endpoint to the tFET and tFELS tests (part of OECD project 2.64 and currently under pre-validation). The OECD DNT zebrafish subgroup is now evaluating the added value of the zebrafish light-dark transition assay to the developmental neurotoxicity in vitro</p>	<p>KE 1005 “Reduced, Swimming performance”</p> <p>Direct evidence linking a reduced swimming performance to reduced survival is largely missing (Handelsman et al., 2010). From a biological perspective it is, however, plausible to assume that reduced swimming performance leads to impaired feeding behaviour, reduced predator avoidance and altered reproductive behaviour.</p> <p>KE 1005 is part of: 5 WPHA/WNT endorsed AOPs: AOPs 155 “Deiodinase 2 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation.” AOP 156 “Deiodinase 2 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation.”</p>	<p>Multiple pathways/factors (ED and non-ED) can influence swimming performance including general changes in energy metabolism such as an increased metabolic cost due to chemical exposure.</p> <p>AOP 242 Inhibition of lysyl oxidase leading to enhanced chronic fish toxicity. AOP 334 Glucocorticoid Receptor Agonism Leading to Impaired Fin Regeneration.</p> <p>Both AOPs are under development</p>		6-propylthiouracil, iopanoic acid, methimazole, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole	<p>Plausibly relevant to fish and amphibian species (and any free-swimming aquatic species)</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to all free-swimming life stages</p> <p>Plausibly relevant to both sexes</p>

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		battery. This assay also includes a swimming performance component.	<p>AOPs 157 "Deiodinase 1 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced posterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>AOP 158 "Deiodinase 1 inhibition leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation."</p> <p>AOP 159 "leading to increased mortality via reduced anterior swim bladder inflation in fish)."</p>				

*as of April 2025

Only well-established, validated or under validation assays are included in this table. Additional, as yet non-validated methods are listed in a recent inventory paper by Vergauwen and colleagues (Vergauwen et al. 2024).

AhR, Aryl-hydrocarbon receptor; AOP, Adverse outcome pathway; AR, Androgen receptor; BPA, Bisphenol A; CAR, Constitutive androstane receptor; DIO, Deiodinase; DNT, Developmental neurotoxicity; ED, Endocrine disruption; ER, Estrogen Receptor; FELS, Fish early life-stage toxicity test, FET, Fish embryo toxicity test; GLP, Good laboratory practice; GR, Glucocorticoid receptor; IATA, Integrated approaches to testing and assessment; iFEDT, integrated Fish Endocrine Disruption Test; KE, Key event; LAT, L-type amino acid transporters ; LXR, Liver X receptor; MCT, Monocarboxylate transporters; MIE, Molecular initiating event; MR, Mineralocorticoid receptor; NIS, Na⁺/I⁻ Symporter; OECD, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; OATP, Organic anion transporting polypeptides; PAH, Polyaromatic hydrocarbon; PBDE, Polybrominated diphenyl ether; PCBs, Polychlorinated biphenyls; PPAR, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor; PTU, Propylthiouracil; RAR, Retinoic acid receptor; ROS, Reactive oxygen species; RXR, Retinoid X receptor; SSNHL, Sudden sensorineural hearing loss; T3, triiodothyronine; T4, thyroxine; TBBPA, Tetrabromobisphenol A; TBG, Thyroxine-binding globulin; TCDD, Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin; TG: Test Guideline; TH; Thyroid hormone; TR: Thyroid hormone receptor, TRH, Thyrotropin-releasing hormone; THSD: Thyroid hormone system disruption, TSH: Thyroid stimulating hormone/thyrotropin; TSHR, Thyroid stimulating hormone receptor; TTR, Thyroxine-binding prealbumin; VDR, Vitamin D receptor; XETA, *Xenopus* Eleutheroembryonic Thyroid Assay

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